

Funded by the European Union

m4estro

Industrial Manufacturing As a Service

Strategies and models for flexible, resilient, and reconfigurable value networks through Trusted and Transparent Operations

M4ESTRO aspires to create a reliable and transparent end-to-end platform using a Manufacturing as a Service (MaaS) approach to offer resilience and timely preparedness to the manufacturing industry during disruptive times.

@M4ESTRO_Project
 M4ESTRO EU Project
 www.m4estro-project.eu

A holistic framework based on 4 pillars

Resilient, transparent and flexible manufacturing processes in value chains

Resilient equipment, AI and trusted data for adaptive manufacturing

Resilient Simulations to the Industrial Metaverse for responsive manufacturing

Human centered Manufacturing Resilience and Sustainability

17 Partners

8 Countries

42 Months

6 Million EU funding

